

Aloidendron ramossissimum

Maiden's Quiver tree

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 1.5 m

Distribution:

Maiden's Quiver Tree is restricted to desert mountainsides and arid ravines in South Africa (Richtersveld of the Northern Cape) and southern Namibia. Its distribution is concentrated within the Ai-Ais Richtersveld Transfrontier Park.

Importance:

Aloidendron ramosissimum is threatened by plant theft, overgrazing, and ongoing habitat degradation. Its slow growth and low resilience mean disturbances, drought, and increased grazing pressure have long-term impacts, especially on juvenile survival. Climate change and possible mining activities are expected to further reduce its suitable habitat.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 379.51 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 12.36 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 11.21 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.9% [Single: 92.7%, Duplicated: 6.8%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 31 335.17 kilobases

Contig number: 14 536

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